

6. J. KLOSA, Ger. 1, 112, 987, appl. July 28, 1959; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 56, 3409 d.
7. G. S. SAHARIA, and M. P. TYAGI *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 508.
8. J. PERKOW, *Arzneimittel-Forsch.*, 1960, 10, 1020.
9. J. PERKOW, *Arzneimittel-Forsch.*, 1960, 10, 478.
10. A. K. EPSSTEIN, and B. R. HARRIS, U.S. 2, 273, 849, Feb. 24; *Chem. Abs.*, 1942, 36, 3905¹.
11. H. PAREKH, A. R. PARIKH, and K. A. THAKER, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 501.

Synthesis and Ion Exchange Properties of New Series of Inorganic Ion Exchangers : VII Hydrous Cerium (IV), Oxide and Thorium Antimonate.

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IN continuation of our work on the development of new inorganic ion exchangers¹⁻⁶, we have found hydrous cerium (IV) oxide and thorium antimonate to have useful ion exchange properties. These belong to the classes of hydrous oxides of metals and insoluble salts of polybasic metals respectively⁷. The present communication summarises our preliminary studies on these inorganic ion exchangers.

Experimental

Reagents: All the chemicals used were of analar grade (B.D.H. or S. Merck).

Apparatus: pH measurements were made with an Elico Model 10 pH meter, Hyderabad, India Spectromom 2.2 (Hungary) was used for spectrophotometric work.

Synthesis: Hydrous cerium (IV) oxide of two different forms were prepared by mixing ceric sulfate and sodium hydroxide solutions in different ratios at room temperature. Crystalline variety was obtained using the normal order of addition of the reagents (ceric sulphate/sodium hydroxide) while amorphous form was obtained by reversing the order of addition (sodium hydroxide/ceric sulphate). In each case the mixture was digested for 2 hr. at room temperature.

Thorium antimonate was prepared by mixing thorium nitrate and potassium pyroantimonate solutions in nitric acid and also by mixing thorium nitrate and antimony pentachloride solutions in different ratios at room temperature. The mixture was digested for 2 hr. at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The compositions of both hydrous cerium (IV) dioxide and thorium antimonate were established by analysis by standard methods. The former had CeO₂ : H₂O ratios 2.58 (crystalline) and 3.00 (amorphous) while the latter had Sb . The ratios 3.67, 4.27 etc. These products are fairly stable in acids of moderate concentrations (upto 0.5 M) and more stable in water and alkali at room temperature.

pH titration curves were obtained by following the method of Topp and Peppers⁸ by shaking intermittently a known weight of the exchanger with different amounts of alkali, MoH (M=Li, Na or K) plus alkali sulphate. The curves indicate monofunctional behaviour of the exchangers. The ion exchange capacities of the exchangers at different pH were determined from the pH titrations. The ion exchange capacities follow the sequence: Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺ < NH₄⁺, which agree with the order of decreasing hydrated ionic radius in the series. With increase in pH, there is increase in the ion exchange capacity values.

Distribution coefficient values of various metal ions were measured at optimum pH 6-8 as reported in our earlier papers¹⁻⁶ and on the basis of these values several selective ion exchange separation schemes have been worked out. Details of these investigations will be published elsewhere.

References

1. A. K. DE and K. CHAUDHURY, *J. Chromatog.* 1974, 101, 63.
2. A. K. DE and K. CHAUDHURY, *J. Chromatog.* 1974, 101, 73.
3. A. K. DE and K. CHAUDHURY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1975, 10, 39.
4. A. K. DE and K. CHAUDHURY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1975, 10, 639.
5. A. K. DE and K. CHAUDHURY, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 137.
6. A. K. DE and S. K. DAS, *Sep. Sci.*, 1976, 11, 183.
7. C. B. AMPHLETT, "Inorganic Ion Exchangers", Elsevier, 1964.
8. N. E. TOPP and K. W. PEPPERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3299.

Copper Thiomalate as an Indicator in the Volumetric Estimation of Rare Earths

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RECENTLY¹ it was reported that copper-thiomalate can be effectively used as an indicator in the volumetric estimation of Al(III), Ga(III) and In(III). The same metal indicator can be successfully employed in